

D6.4: Call Announcement and Guide for Applicants for 2nd Open Call

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Abstract	This document contains requirements for Open Call applicants: an Open Call Announcement, a Guide for Applicants, Technical Guidelines and Budget template.
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CHANGE CONTROL

Date	Version	Editor	Changes to document
2025/04/24	v1.0	Antonio Montalvo	First release

Important remarks:

- The contributors listed in this table and on the front page are the report's primary editing authors. It is important to note that all COROB partners are contributing critical technical contributions to this ongoing work.

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Nature of the deliverable:	R	
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)	✓
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/ EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	
Classified C-UE/ EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	
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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc.

DMP: Data management plan

ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues.

SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D6.4 aims to provide guidance and requirements for the COROB 2nd Open Call applicants. The following list provides documents included in this Deliverable:

- Call Announcement
- Guide for Applicants
- Technical Guidelines
- Budget Template

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COROB 2ND OPEN CALL ANNOUNCEMENT

Call Announcement	
Call title:	COROB 2nd OPEN CALL
Full name of the EU-funded project:	Cooperative robotics powered by AI and data for flexible production cells
Project acronym:	COROB
Grant agreement number:	101120640
Call publication date:	20/01/2025
Call deadline:	21/03/2025
Expected duration of participation:	6 months for Funding Instrument: Solutions to challenges Stage 1 'Individual Mentoring Plan' Stage 2 'Solution development' Stage 3 'Solution Validation'
Total EU funding available:	€ 140,000 (COROB 2nd Open Call)
Submission & evaluation process:	<p>Submission through the application form available at: https://corob-2-oc.fundingbox.com/</p> <p>The selection of the Open Call proposals will be carried out in a five steps process.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Step one will be first check of the applications - Step two will involve independent evaluators to assess the proposal according to the criteria. - Step three will involve the COROB Consensus Group to agree on a common position, including comments and scores for all evaluated proposals. - Step four will involve the 'Selection Committee' to decide the 'Provisional List of FSTP recipients' and 'Reserve List'. - Step five will check the ethical aspects and formal check of the pre-selected beneficiaries. <p>For further information see the 'Guide for Applicants'.</p>
Further information:	<p>Application form: https://corob-2-oc.fundingbox.com/</p> <p>OC helpdesk: https://discord.com/invite/aMKmU5KdmH</p> <p>OC website: https://corob-2-oc.fundingbox.com/</p> <p>OC complaints email: corob.complaints@fundingbox.com</p> <p>Project website: https://www.corob-project.eu/</p>
Task description:	<p>The exact amount of financial support to be granted to 2 selected entities under COROB 2nd Open Call is a fixed lump sum of up to EUR 70,000 per entity Funding Instrument: Solutions to Challenges. SMEs will be funded at a reimbursement rate of 70% of their eligible costs and Start-ups at 100%. Selected entities other than SMEs and start-ups will not be funded but will receive technical support from the COROB project.</p>

Additional information

COROB is a HORIZON EUROPE project co-funded by the European Commission. It is coordinated by LORTEK with the participation of 8 Consortium Partners from 5 countries (see details at <https://www.corob-project.eu/>).

Based on the results of the first Open Call, COROB will launch this additional **Open Call**, aiming to distribute a total maximum amount of **EUR 140,000** and to select up to 2 external solutions that will be tested, validated, and demonstrated through the COROB use cases.

In this Open Call COROB will be focused on the following Funding Instrument: “**Solutions to challenges**” to fund up to 2 technology providers aimed to develop technical solutions covering up to 2 use-case challenges, to be further integrated and validated in the COROB project use cases.

COROB 2nd Open Call is looking for individual entities. The entities eligible for funding can be SMEs and Start-ups. Other entities (companies of any size) are eligible to participate in the open call, but they cannot receive any funding.

GUIDE FOR APPLICANTS

COROB 2nd OPEN CALL

Submission of applications starts: *January 20th, 2025 at 8:00 Brussels Time*

Submission deadline: *March 21th, 2025 at 17:00 Brussels Time*

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1. Basic Info about COROB

COROB is a HORIZON EUROPE project co-funded by the European Commission. It is coordinated by LORTEK with the participation of 8 Consortium Partners from 5 countries (see details at <https://www.corob-project.eu/>).

COROB aims to develop a flexible, cooperative and intelligent multi-robotic solution for arc welding-based manufacturing processes (joining and additive manufacturing), to offer new operational capabilities that allow to increase the efficiency and improve the flexibility of industrial processes.

Conceived as a global solution, COROB will employ a cooperative multi-robot system powered by Inspection, Monitoring, Control and AI techniques to optimise the welding process, and the adjacent manufacturing stages for time, cost, energy, and resource reduction.

The data generated will be processed in a data acquisition platform to feed the AI technologies, addressing optimisation, search, planning, and analysis, ensuring AI robustness and trustworthiness.

Robots have historically been employed in businesses involving mass manufacturing to carry out repetitive activities at reasonable costs and quality standards, giving up flexibility in exchange for efficiency. Multiple robots working together and using AI and data technologies provide enhanced operating capabilities in many industrial processes by enhancing their manoeuvrability and manipulability. For flexible and reconfigurable manufacturing to meet HMLV¹ industrial production demands in the present technological framework of Industry 5.0, COROB suggests developing an intelligent cooperative multi-robotic system. Innovations in robotics, inspection, monitoring, control, and artificial intelligence (AI) developed by consortium partners and external third parties solutions will be integrated into the human-centric system. It will contribute to resilience, resource-saving, circular economy, cost savings, and digital supply chain, fostering European industrial competitiveness.

In COROB the solution will be validated in two semi-industrial use cases focused on arc-welding joining and Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM), also referred as Directed Energy Deposition-Arc (DED-Arc) for repairing. The provided solution at the end of the project may be scaled and replicated to additional processes such as assembly, painting, and finishing. Manufacturing processes will utilise cutting-edge technology, including cooperative and intelligent robotic solutions while keeping humans involved to create a more sustainable and competitive sector. The use cases have been chosen to be complementary so that the validation is representative enough for different potential scenarios of application, maximising the impact and ensuring the future transferability of COROB technologies to other sectors or manufacturing processes.

USE CASE 1

This use case will focus on a cooperative multi-robot system for flexible manufacturing. The welding process will be performed using a jigless robotic approach, defined as robotic welding without tools/jigs in which two manipulator robots hold and present the workpieces to one welding robot.

¹ HMLV - High-Mix Low-Volume.

USE CASE 2

This use case will deploy a multi-robot cooperative robotic cell for the repair of tooling. The main industrial robot will be responsible for the processing operations, equipped with a Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) or else referred as Direct Energy Deposition Arc (DED-Arc) head as an end effector, taking care of the repair tasks. Together with a 2-DoF² rotary table, it will constitute an 8-DoF processing system, capable of repairing very complex geometries.

Additionally, a smaller, collaborative robot will be integrated in the cell and will be responsible for the auxiliary processing tasks. A core technology integrated in the robot will be 3D scanning, while other technologies (e.g. inspection, part treatment, finishing, etc.) will be examined through the Open Calls of the project.

Based on the results of the first Open Call, COROB will launch this additional **Open Call**, aiming to distribute a total maximum amount of **EUR 140,000** and to select up to 2 external solutions that will be tested, validated, and demonstrated through the COROB use cases.

In this Open Call COROB will be focused on the following Funding Instrument: “**Solutions to challenges**” to fund up to 2 technology providers aimed to develop technical solutions covering up to 2 use-case challenges, to be further integrated and validated in the COROB project use cases.

² DoF" refers to "Degrees of Freedom," indicating that the rotary table can independently rotate along two axes. Considering the robot arm's 6 joints, the total degrees of freedom sum up to 8.

2. What do we offer?

The exact amount of financial support to be granted to each selected entity under COROB 2nd Open Call is a fixed lump sum of up to EUR 70,000³.

Based on the budget presented, Start-ups⁴ will be covered for 100% of their eligible costs, while SMEs⁵ that are not Start-ups can receive 70% of their eligible costs, with the remaining 30% to be self-funded.

NOTE! Companies⁶ of any size, other than SMEs and Start-ups, are welcome to apply, but only SMEs and Start-ups can receive financial support. If selected, other types of companies will receive only technical support from the COROB consortium partners. Such companies must cover 100% of their costs independently.

3. Eligibility Criteria

To participate in the COROB programme you have to meet all the criteria described in Section 3 of this Guide, positively pass our evaluation process and finally sign the Subgrant Agreement with COROB Consortium.

The projects that do not comply with the criteria described in this section will be excluded. We will check the eligibility criteria during the whole evaluation process.

3.1 Who are we looking for?

We are looking for individual entities. The entities eligible for funding can be SMEs and Start-ups. Other companies of any size are eligible to participate in the Open Call, but they cannot receive any funding. It is essential to highlight that non-profit organisations are not eligible to apply for this Open Call.

The entities have to be established in any of the:

- [The Member States of the European Union⁷](#) and its Overseas Countries and Territories (OCT)

³ This amount could be decreased depending on the quality and the accomplishments of the requested deliverables during the milestones review (see section 5)

⁴ **Start-up** refers to a tech-oriented company. It should employ less than 10 people (but more than 2 full time equivalent staff) that has operated for less than three years and has attracted more than €50k early stage private sector investment or has demonstrable sales growth over 50% pa.

⁵ An **SME** will be considered as such if it complies with the European Commission's Recommendation 2003/361/EC. As a summary, the criteria defining an SME are:

- Headcount in Annual Work Unit (AWU) less than 250;
- Annual turnover less or equal to €50 million OR annual balance sheet total less or equal to €43 million.

Note that the figures of partners and linked enterprises should also be considered as stated in the SME user guide. For detailed information check EU recommendation:

https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/business-friendly-environment/sme-definition_en

⁶ A **Company** is a for-profit entity.

⁷ Following the Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/2506, as of 16th December 2022, no legal commitments can be signed with Hungarian public interest trusts established under Hungarian Act IX of 2021 or any entity they maintain. Affected entities may continue to apply to calls for proposals. However, in case the Council measures are not lifted, such entities are not eligible to participate in the COROB Open Call. In case of consortium, co-applicants will be invited to remove or replace that entity. Tasks and budget may be redistributed accordingly.

- [Associated Countries \(AC\) to Horizon Europe⁸](#) .

The applicants who are subject to EU restrictive measures under Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU)⁹ are not eligible to participate in this open call.

The COROB Consortium partners, their affiliated entities, employees or permanent collaborators CANNOT be involved in the grantees' projects. They are not eligible to act as applicants in the COROB Open Call.

3.2 What types of activities can be funded?

- Funding Instrument: Solutions to challenges

The activities should address the development of technological solutions and systems applicable to one of the 2 use cases of the COROB project: multi-robot cooperative welding and multi-robot cooperative WAAM, in the identified challenges. Therefore, the activities that qualify for financial support will cover the development and integration of NDT methods for monitoring and quality inspection, considering problematic environments, including:

- CH 1: Preheating systems integrated in the robot.
- CH 2: Obtain real CAD and quality check in pre-process and post-process stages. Virtual validation.

The solutions will use, whenever possible, common resources from other digital resource platforms ([AI-onDemand platform](#), [Digital Industrial platform for Robotics](#), amongst others).

The activities that qualify for financial support have to fall within the scope of the COROB project, which is to develop a flexible, cooperative and intelligent multi-robotic solution for arc welding-based manufacturing processes (joining and additive manufacturing), to offer new operational capabilities that allow to increase the efficiency and improve the flexibility of industrial processes.

Please find a link to the '[Technical Guidelines](#)' where you can find a more detailed description of the challenges.

Your project should have a clear European Dimension, meaning fostering projects that generate a substantial positive impact for European citizens.

When applying to the COROB 2nd Open Call, please note that all activities need to start at TRL¹⁰ 4-5 and finish at TRL 5-6. You can find examples of ideal projects in the '[Technical](#)

⁸ AC as of 16.12.2024: Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Canada, Faroe Islands, Georgia, Iceland, Israel, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia, Tunisia, Türkiye, Ukraine, United Kingdom. For the most up-to-date list please first part of [this document](#).

⁹ Please note that the EU Official Journal contains the official list and, in case of conflict, its content prevails over that of the EU Sanctions Map.

¹⁰ TRL - Technology Readiness Level - Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) are indicators of the maturity level of particular technologies. This measurement system provides a common understanding of technology status and addresses the entire innovation chain. There are nine technology readiness levels; TRL 1 being the lowest and TRL

[Guidelines](#)' where the two challenges are described in detail. Please note that the initial and final TRL's can not be at the same level.

3.3 Ground rules

Proposals must be submitted through the COROB microsite:

<https://corob-2-oc.fundingbox.com/>

When applying to COROB 2nd Open Call, please also note that:

- **Be on time and use our system:** Make sure you submit your proposal through the COROB 2nd Open Call microsite before the deadline of March 21st, 2025 at 17:00 Brussels Time. If you submit the form correctly, the system will send you a confirmation of your submission. Get in touch with us if it is not the case.
- **English Language:** your proposal must be written in English in all mandatory parts to be eligible. Only parts written in English will be evaluated. If the mandatory parts of the proposal are in any other language, the entire proposal will be rejected. If only non-mandatory parts of a proposal are submitted in a language different from English, those parts will not be evaluated, but the proposal is still eligible.
- **Every question deserves your attention:** all mandatory sections - generally marked with an asterisk - of your proposal must be completed. The data provided should be actual, true, and complete and should allow assessment of the proposal. Additional material not specifically requested in the online application form will not be considered for the evaluation.
- **Be exhaustive:** You have to verify the completeness of the form, as it won't be possible to add any further information after the deadline. After the proposal is submitted, you will be able to modify the form until March 21st, 2025 at 17:00 Brussels Time.
- **Multiple submissions:** Applicants may submit up to 2 proposals, each addressing a different challenge offered by COROB. Though applicants could submit multiple applications, neither team members nor any entities can be funded twice by COROB. In the case that more than one proposal with any similar team members or from the same organisation will be among the selected projects, only the highest-ranked proposal will be funded.
- **Conflicts of interest:** we will take into consideration the existence of a potential **conflict of interest** among you and one or more Consortium partners. Consortium partners, their affiliated entities, employees, or persons treated as personnel (ex. working under B2B contract) cannot take part in the COROB programme. All cases of potential conflict of interest will be assessed case by case.
- **Healthy finances and a clean sheet are a must:** we don't accept entities that are under liquidation or are an enterprise under difficulty according to the Commission Regulation No 651/2014, art. 2.18, or that are excluded from the possibility of obtaining EU funding under the provisions of both national and EU law, or by a

9 the highest. In our project, we refer to Annex B of the [General Annexes for Horizon Europe Work Programme 2021-2022](#) for a full description of TRLs.

decision of both national or EU authority. We also don't accept entities that are meeting national regulations regarding bankruptcy.

- **It is your proposal:** your project should be based on your original work or your right to use the IPR must be clear. Going forward, any foreseen developments must be free from third-party rights, or those third-party rights must be clearly stated. Any work related to the implementation of the project described in the application may not violate the IPR of third parties, and the IPR of the application project may not be the subject of a dispute or proceedings for infringement of third-party IPR. However, during the lifetime of the COROB project, you should grant the COROB Consortium partners access to the background and results generated within your project. If you do not consent on this, your proposal cannot be eligible.
- **Scope.** The objectives of the proposal must fit within the scope of the project as it is described in section 3.2 of this Guide for Applicants.
- **Submission and modification of the Applications:** It will not be possible to update any information or modify your proposal application after the deadline. The only exception is if a mistake has been made in the key administrative data (e.g. contact mail or phone, name of the company, etc.). In this case, the applicants have to contact us by e-mail indicating the proposal ID, their username, and the data which should be corrected.
- **Acceptance of the open call rules:** to apply for this open call you have to accept its rules and regulations detailed in this Guide for applicants.
- COROB is planning a certain number of online webinars about this Open Call. They will be announced at the [COROB 2nd Open Call Microsite](#) and in the Connected World Community in [Discord](#).

If you need extra hints on how to prepare your application, check out the section: [extra Hints to submit your proposal](#).

4. How will we evaluate your proposal?

Our evaluation process is transparent, fair and equal to all our participants with a clearly defined complaint procedure (see section [Contact us](#)). We will evaluate your project in 6 phases. We encourage you to put in the effort to present your project in the best possible way, offering as much detail as you can. This will assist us in evaluating your application and identifying how your proposal aligns with the overall scope of COROB.

Figure 1 - COROB Selection process

4.1 STEP 1: First Check

After the closure of the Open Call, we will review the proposal to ensure it meets the conditions outlined in Section 3. This assessment will be based on the statements provided in your proposal.

At this stage, the eligibility criteria are checked against the Declaration of Honour or self-declarations included in the application form, and they will be continuously verified throughout the evaluation process, including the final formal check.

Projects that do not comply with the above-mentioned criteria will be rejected. We will inform you about the results of this basic/initial check.

4.2 STEP 2: Independent Individual Evaluation

In this phase, each project will be evaluated by two Independent Experts. They will be appointed according to the specific characteristics of the applicants from the COROB's pool of External Experts.

These external experts must be independent¹¹ from the applicants and cannot be Consortium partners employees, permanent collaborators, nor board members.

¹¹ By 'independent from the applicants' we refer to "they cannot be personnel working for the applicant under an employment contract (or equivalent appointing act); they cannot be a person who works under conditions similar to those of an employee (under direct contract) and SMEs (partner of a consortium) owner or similar situations".

The projects will be evaluated within the following awarding criteria:

1. EXCELLENCE will evaluate:

- **Ambition:** The applicants have to demonstrate to what extent the proposed solutions contribute to the project scope and have a human-centred approach. In particular identifying the COROB challenge they will tackle, and how. They have to describe the innovative approach behind it (e.g. ground-breaking objectives, novel concepts and approaches or new products, services).
- **Innovation:** The applicants should provide information about the level of innovation within their market and about the degree of differentiation that this project will bring, as well as a brief analysis of the State-of-the-Art and what is the project contribution beyond it.
- **Soundness of the approach and credibility of the proposed methodology** for covering the challenge, and the needs and steps for integration / interoperability with the use cases of COROB.

2. IMPACT will analyse:

- **Advancing AI, Data and Robotics:** the applicants will have to demonstrate their added value for a flexible and intelligent manufacturing environment using robotics powered by AI and Data, in alignment with COROB proposed technologies.
- **Market opportunity and Scalability:** The applicants have to demonstrate the level of market potential of their solutions for multi-robot systems in the sectors of the use cases and its scalability in other areas and processes, for maximising their business opportunities.
- **Competition:** The applicants have to describe and analyse the degree of competition of your product/service and to what extent your proposal is disruptive and breaks to the market, i.e. the products/services to be brought to market can be clearly differentiated from the competition.
- **Environmental and social impact:** The applicants have to demonstrate the project contribution, aligned with COROB objectives, towards environmental, social and economic impacts to contribute to sustainable development and Green Deal targets, as well as a substantial positive impact for European citizens (European Dimension).

3. IMPLEMENTATION will consider:

- **Work Plan:** The work plan of the applicant's proposal has to be clearly described and fully aligned with the objectives, including Work packages and tasks. The time plan should be realistic and achievable, coherent and effective. A risk assessment should also be provided.
- **Team:** The applicants have to demonstrate their management and leadership qualities, their ability to take a concept from ideas to market, their capacity to carry through their ideas and understand the dynamics of the market they are trying to tap into. The team

should be a cross functional team, with a strong background and skills base and taking into account its gender balance.

- **Resources:** Demonstrate the quality and effectiveness of the resources assigned in order to get the objectives/deliverables proposed. Start-ups will be funded 100% of their eligible costs, but in the case of SMEs the compromise of 30% self-financing of activities should be secured by each beneficiary. For applicants not having start-up or SME status, the compromise of 100% self-financing of activities should be secured by each beneficiary. The applicants will have to upload a budget estimation in pdf, by fulfilling the corresponding tab in Excel table provided [here](#).

The evaluators will score each award criterion on a scale from 0 to 5:

0 = Proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information

1 = Poor – criterion is inadequately addressed or there are serious inherent weaknesses

2 = Fair – proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses

3 = Good – proposal addresses the criterion well, but a number of shortcomings are present

4 = Very good – proposal addresses the criterion very well, but a small number of shortcomings are present

5 = Excellent – proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

Each proposal will be evaluated by 2 independent experts. Each evaluator will produce an Individual Evaluation Report. Once the Individual Evaluation Reports are submitted, the final score for each individual criterion will be calculated as the average of the scores provided by each evaluator. The final score of each application will be calculated as the sum of the scores for each criterion.

The final score per application will be calculated as the sum of the score for each individual criterion. The threshold for individual criteria will be 3. The overall threshold, applying to the sum of the three individual scores, is 10 points.

4.3 STEP 3: Evaluation Consensus Group

After carrying out the 'Independent Individual Evaluation', external experts who have evaluated the proposals will join a Consensus Group, to agree on a common position, including comments and scores for all evaluated proposals.

The Consensus Group will specially discuss the cases where there is a significant divergence between the evaluators' scoring. In case no consensus is reached between the evaluators, an additional evaluator will be included to provide an extra evaluation.

In case of ties, the following criteria will be used to rank the projects, in order:

- The highest score in the Impact Section;
- Gender balance among the personnel responsible for carrying out the activities.

As a result of the Independent Evaluation, a 'Ranking List' will be produced.

All proposals obtaining a score above the threshold -including the results of the Evaluation Consensus Group- will pass to the next phase. Please note that we need time to process through all the proposals in this phase, so you probably will not hear back from us until the process is done.

4.4 STEP 4: Consensus Meeting

The 'Selection Committee' -with the potential support of two external experts and the ethics expert (with voice but without vote)- will decide by consensus (minimum $\frac{2}{3}$ of the votes) the list of applicants to pass to the next phase. The discussion will be based on the ranking obtained from the previous step.

In order to ensure the two proposed challenges are supported, the 'Selection Committee' will make sure that the highest ranked proposal per challenge will be funded.

Bear in mind that even if it is normally the best-marked proposals that are selected for funding, the Selection Committee may have fair reasons for objecting to the selection of a specific candidate. These reasons can relate to:

- The alignment with COROB goals and scope.
- The ability to achieve the strongest possible impact.
- Commercial competition.
- The existence of significant ethical concerns.
- The existence of a potential conflict of interest¹²

4.5 STEP 5: Ethics Assessment

The 'Ethics Assessment' will be done by an ethics expert according to the ethical guidelines of Horizon EU. The resulting 'Ethics Summary Report' may lead to include either specific requirements (contractual obligation) in the ethics section of the Sub-Grant Agreement and/or countermeasures tackling Ethical issues within the Individual Mentoring Plans. Beneficiaries must provide thorough answers to the Ethics Requirement queries before final approval and disbursement of funds.

4.6 Formal Check, Sub-grant Agreement Preparation and Signature

Before you get started with the COROB programme, you need to sign the Sub-grant Agreement with the COROB Consortium.

Before signing the Agreement, you should provide documents regarding your formal status. The COROB Consortium will verify them to prove your eligibility.

Be extremely vigilant with respect to:

1. The nature of the documents we request.

If the documents you provide do not prove your eligibility, the process will end here for you.

2. The deadlines that we will give you to hand us these documents.

If you do not deliver the requested documents on time, without a clear and reasonable justification, we will have to exclude you from further formal assessment. Another applicant from the 'Reserve List' will then replace you.

¹² Please note that this is not a closed list of reasons.

5. Our Support Programme and Payment Arrangements

Once your eligibility has been confirmed following the formal check and the Sub-grant Agreement signed, you will become an official beneficiary of the COROB programme. As a selected grantee, you will receive a fixed lump sum of up to EUR 70,000. The Support Programme will last 6 months.

The lump sum is a simplified method of settling expenses in projects financed from Horizon Europe funds. It means that the grantee is not required to present strictly defined accounting documents to prove the cost incurred (e.g. invoices), but is obliged to demonstrate that the implementation of the project is in line with the milestones set for it. Simply speaking, it means that we will carefully assess your progress and the quality of your work during Interim Reviews. The milestones (deliverables, KPIs¹³ and ethical recommendations) will be set in the 'Individual Mentoring Plan' elaborated at the beginning of the programme.

The lump sum method does not exempt you from collecting documentation to confirm the costs under fiscal regulations.

Payment Arrangements

Payment milestones	Deliverable	Delivery Date	Payment Date	Amount (EUR)
Stage 1 IMP	D1 IMP ¹⁴	M01	M02	Up to 11,900
Stage 2. Solution development	D2 Solution development report	M04	M05	Up to 29,750
Stage 3. Validation	D3 Final report	M06	M06+1	Up to 17,850
FINAL PAYMENT		Withheld amount due	September 30 th 2026 + 9 months	Up to 10,500
TOTAL				Up to 70,000

Table 1 Payment Milestones for Funding Instrument: Solutions to challenges

A delayed payment mechanism will be applied to the final payment. 15% of the total grant amount - up to EUR 10,125 - will be paid to the beneficiaries who completed the final stage once the whole COROB project is completed. This should happen approximately 9 months after the end of the Project. The expected end of the COROB project is September 30th, 2026. Relevant

¹³ KPI stands for key performance indicator, a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective. KPIs provide targets for teams to shoot for, milestones to gauge progress, and insights that help people across the organisation make better decisions.

¹⁴ The Individual Mentoring Plan [IMP] is the document that establishes the individual budget, KPIs, Deliverables and a schedule that will be taken into account when evaluating the FSTP recipients' performance at the Milestones Review.

provisions will be included in the Sub-grant Agreements. Please bear in mind that the COROB project might be extended.

A Milestone Review will be organised for each payment milestone established at the project level.

	Funding Instrument: Solutions to challenges
1 st Milestone Review	Individual Mentoring Plan (IMP)
2 nd Milestone Review	Solution development
3 rd Milestone Review	Solution Validation

Table 3 Milestones Review

The evaluation of the beneficiaries' performance at the Milestone Review will be done by the Technical and Business mentors and Ethics Partners (in the case of beneficiaries where specific requirements on ethics have been included as deliverable in the Individual Mentoring Plan).

The assessment of the IMP will be based on an approved or not approved approach.

The evaluation of the the other two deliverables will be done based on the following criteria:

- Deliverables' quality (Weight 30%)
- Technical and/or Business performance indicators (Weight 60%)
- Deadline Compliance (Weight 10%)

If applicable, an Ethical deliverable will be submitted at the end of Stage 3 and evaluated by the Ethics Partners. Its approval will be a condition to the last payment.

Each criterion will be scored from 0 to 10 and, based on the weight of each criteria, the final score will be calculated. The total score will be obtained based on the weight of each mentor: Technical mentors (70%), Business mentors (30%).

The threshold to continue in the programme is 7 points. The 'Selection Committee' will review and validate the evaluations, putting special attention to the 'under threshold' cases, if any, by taking into consideration all possible objective reasons for underperformance (i.e. external factors which might have influenced the beneficiaries' performance). The 'Selection Committee' will make the final decision, and approve the payments or invite beneficiaries which have not reached the threshold to leave the programme.

6. Contact us

How can we help you?

If you have any questions regarding our application process, feel free to post your questions in the Connected World Helpdesk in [Discord](#). [Here](#) you can find out how to access the Community.

In case of any technical issues or problems, please include the following information in your message:

- Your username, phone number and email address;
- Details of the specific problem (e.g. error messages you encountered, bug description, i.e. if a dropdown list isn't working, etc.);
- Screenshots of the problem.

Complaints

If you believe that a mistake has been made after receiving the results of one of the evaluation phases (when foreseen), you may submit a complaint. To do so, please email us your complaint in English at corob.complaints@fundingbox.com and include the following information:

- Your contact details (including email address);
- The subject of the complaint;
- Information and evidence regarding the alleged breach.

You have **3 calendar days** to submit your complaint, starting from the day after the communication was sent. We will review your complaint within seven calendar days of its reception. If we need more time to assess your complaint, we will inform you about the extension by email. We will not review anonymous complaints as well as complaints with incomplete information.

Please take into account that the evaluation is run by experts in the relevant field, and we do not interfere with their assessment. Therefore, we will not evaluate complaints related to the results of the evaluation other than those related to procedural or technical mistakes.

7. Last but not least - final provisions

Any matters not covered by this Guide will be governed by Polish law and rules related to the Horizon Europe and EU grants.

Please take into account that we make our best effort to keep all provided data confidential; however, for the avoidance of doubt, you are solely responsible to indicate your confidential information as such. Your IPR will remain your property, but as stated in section 3, during the lifetime of the COROB project, you need to grant the COROB Consortium partners access to the background and results generated within your project. Further agreements may be needed in case of IPR generated from work carried out jointly by you and one or more COROB Partners after the COROB project has ended.

For the selected grantees, the Sub-grant agreement will include the set of obligations towards the European Commission (for example: promoting the project and giving visibility to the EU funding, maintaining confidentiality, understanding potential controls by the EC/ECA, EPPO and OLAF).

The COROB Consortium might cancel the call at any time, change its provisions or extend it. In such a case we will inform all applicants about such change. Signature of the Sub-grant agreement is an initial condition to establish any obligations among applicants and any Consortium partners (with respect to the obligation of confidentiality of the application).

Did not find what you were looking for? [Contact us](#) and we will happily answer all your questions.

8. Extra hints before you submit your proposal

A proposal takes time and effort and we know it. Here are a few crucial points you should read before submitting your proposal.

- Is your project in line with what COROB is looking for? You are not sure? You can consult this [section](#) and this [one](#).
- Did you present your project in a way that will convince evaluators? Not sure if you did? Go back to this [section](#).
- Is your project fulfilling all eligibility requirements described in the Guide? Check again this [section](#).
- Are you sure you are able to cope with our process of the Sub-grant agreement signature and payment arrangements for selected proposals? You may want to go over this [section](#).
- Did you check our Sub-grant agreement template? You didn't? Check it [here](#).

Do you need extra help? [Contact us](#)

MEET THE CONSORTIUM

TECHNICAL GUIDELINES

COROB 2nd OPEN CALL

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INTRODUCTION

To ensure its alignment with the COROB project, applicants are requested to propose solutions or experiments in compliance with a set of technical requirements that are grouped in two main categories:

- Solutions to challenges should address the development of technology and systems solutions applicable to both use cases of the COROB project: multi-robot cooperative welding and multi-robot cooperative WAAM, in the identified challenges. Integration and testing of innovative technologies to enhance the capabilities of the project's use-cases.
- Experiments for Enabling technologies for digital services are activities for digital services linked to the deployment of the multi-robot systems in the project's use cases. These experiments should be interoperable with the project's data acquisition platform for efficient data processing.

The following sections provide more information of these requirements. The “Technical Guidelines” includes the necessary templates, background materials and explanations to assist in preparing a successful application from the technical perspective.

1. PREHEATING SYSTEMS INTEGRATED IN THE ROBOT

Directed Energy Deposition-Arc (DED-Arc) also referred to as Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM), is a manufacturing process that uses an electric arc as the heat source to melt and deposit metal wire layer by layer, to form three-dimensional shapes. Within COROB, the Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW) WAAM technique is used, focusing on the repair of large-scale tooling. The processing head is manipulated by a 6-DOF industrial robot. An auxiliary collaborative robot with 10kg payload capacity, is employed for executing process supportive tasks. One supportive task that is proposed to be funded and enabled through this open call, is the development of a preheating system of the workpiece to be repaired, which will help in reducing the first layer cracking when using difficult-to-deposit materials and achieve higher build-up rates. From the proposed system the following are expected:

Deliverable:

- The system shall include all the hardware and software components necessary for its operation.

Operation:

- Its operation shall be conducted by the human operator in the collaborative mode of the auxiliary collaborative robot.
- The heating element should be designed to undergo on/off automatically, without human intervention, therefore designed to be able to be controlled (Temperature, On/Off) through software.
- Any digital support for the operator included will be considered an advantage.

Design Requirements:

- Sensorization for monitoring the achieved on the workpiece temperature is needed. It will be considered an advantage if a thermal camera is installed in order monitor the achieved temperatures on the workpiece and display the temperature field to the human operator through a graphical user interface.
- The system shall be developed to be mounted in the collaborative robot as an end-effector.
- Considering the collaborative operation, necessary gripping mechanisms to guide the heating element in an ergonomic manner will be considered as an advantage.
- The overall weight of the proposed solution should not exceed 3-5kg, as it will be mounted on a collaborative robot with 10kg payload capacity (accounting for the reduction in effective payload when the mass is positioned at an extended reach).
- The robot side flange of the system and overall all contact points of the system with the collaborative robot should not surpass the temperature of 45°C, for safety reasons (mainly electronics). The beneficiary should provide evidence that the solution does not surpass that limit or integrate a cooling system in order to ensure that temperature.
- The beneficiary should conduct research on the necessary safety systems that should be deployed overall for the proper operation of this solution in an industrial environment and consider these during the system design.
- The beneficiary should select among the suitable heating method and heating elements.

Process Requirements:

- The heating on the to-be processed area of the workpiece should be as uniform as possible and the preheating process should be performed in an industrial-viable timeframe.
- The beneficiary should conduct research on the desired preheating temperatures focusing on steel alloys.
- The surface areas to be heated may be considered as medium sized, ranging from 40mmx40mm to 500mmx200mm.

2. OBTAIN REAL CAD OF MANUFACTURED PARTS FOR QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Conventional welding workstation consist of a welding robot, a positioner, and a tooling. In the case of high-mix low-volume (HMLV) production scenarios, different complex and expensive jigs and fixtures are required for each reference. The COROB project poses a cooperative multi-robot system for flexible manufacturing. A gas metal arc welding (GMAW) process will be performed using a jigless robotic approach. In a jigless arc welding setup with two manipulator robots and one welding robot, the two manipulators are responsible for precisely positioning and aligning the workpieces, while the welding robot controls the welding torch. Apart from the geometry of the welding bead itself, the overall geometry of the welded parts plays a vital role in the quality inspection during the postprocessing. For geometrical quality inspection of the manufactured parts a 3D scanning is envisioned.

There are different systems on the market based on these techniques (stereoscopic, laser triangulation, etc.) that allow the acquisition of this information in a robust, reliable way and with high quality data. The most convenient technology will be presented for the given use case.

A four-step sequence is suggested:

- Data capture: in this step the manufactured product is scanned, and a point cloud is obtained. Data capture can be by means of a camera, a laser scanner, or other technologies. The manufactured part will be manipulated by a 6-DOF industrial robot and presented to the stand still acquisition hardware.
- Point cloud reconstruction: this phase encompasses the necessary processing of the point cloud, if necessary. Typically, this step covers the necessary roto-translations, correction of overlapping and underlapping points, detection of outliers and blind spots, smoothening, and others.
- CAD conversion: converting the processed point cloud into a CAD file.
- Assessment: comparison of the measured CAD against the theoretical CAD and obtain quantitative metrics with the results.

Optionally, it would be appreciated to add a prior step to calculate the necessary points of inspection for a given CAD. These points will be then transmitted to the manipulation robot to position the part (the generation of collision free trajectories covering these points will be out of the scope of this solution).

The parts to be inspected will be metallic parts installed on a robotic cell in an industrial facility, where shines or reflections may appear and with uncontrolled lighting conditions. The solution should be scalable to scan parts of multiple sizes (10-140 cm).

The provided equipment, including software, shall be easy to install and use, and the results shall be easily interpretable and exportable. The software should be able to connect with the COROB platform to communicate results and a minimum coordination.

There is no hard constrain for the scanning time, as long as reasonable (i.e. few minutes is acceptable). The beneficiary will have to closely collaborate with the COROB consortium for its implementation in accordance with the COROB software architecture.

The final solution shall consist of the hardware for data capture and software execution, and the necessary software, including licenses if required. If the acquisition equipment cannot be installed on a magnetic arm, or equivalent, the given solution shall also provide the installation fixture. The supply of any robot is out of the scope.

MEET THE CONSORTIUM

BUDGET TEMPLATE

Selected Third Party	Name of the entity			Justification of costs
Personnel cost (technical and administrative person-months needed to implement the granted Experiment including R&D for TRL improvement, Experiment-related training and activities with the consortium partners, license and IPR agreement development)	<i>[Person-months]</i>	<i>Average-monthly rate]</i>	<i>#VALUE!</i>	Please detail the roles of personnel involved, hours devoted to the experiment, monthly cost and total cost per person.
Other Direct Costs				
<i>Necessary travel costs for industry partner visits or Experiment- related presentations or demonstrations organized by COROB</i>				Please detail the number of trips, persons traveling and cost per trip and person
<i>Costs for providing open access to scientific publications directly related to the Experiment</i>				Please detail the scientific publications (if any) related to the experiment
<i>Consumables</i>				Please detail the consumables related to the experiment
<i>Equipment costs</i>				Please detail the equipment related to the experiment
<i>Subcontracting costs</i>				Please detail the subcontracting related to the experiment
<i>Overheads (25% of Personnel and Other direct costs) [Total Overheads: 25%*(D2+B4+B5+B6+B7)]</i>	<i>#VALUE!</i>			
Total estimated budget Third Party (EUR) [Total eligible costs: D2+B4+B5+B6+B7+B8]	<i>#VALUE!</i>			

Financial Support reimbursement rate (%)	<i>Insert % [Start-ups: 100%; SMEs: 70%; Other companies: 0%]</i>
Requested Financial Support estimated (EUR) [B9*B11]	<i>#VALUE!</i>